

Report from GAIA photometry work in Lund, 26–30 March 2001

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Kucinskas and Vasevicius visited Lund Observatory during the week 26–30 March 2001 for discussions related to GAIA photometry and astrometry. Fabricius participated in the discussions on 26 and 29 March; on the latter date, also Knude participated.

Topics discussed focused on (1) use of astrometric data as an aid to stellar classification; (2) requirements on the MBP system from chromaticity correction; (3) possible improvements of the classification method. This report summarises the conclusions and agreed actions.

1. Use of astrometric data

The evaluation of possible GAIA photometric systems performed by the Vilnius group uses a Galaxy model to obtain realistic distributions of the stars and their parameters. This is based on the Barcelona model (Torra et al., BA 8, 171, 1999). In the evaluations made thus far (of the 1F, 2A and 3G systems), the astrometric information has not been considered. It is obvious, however, that for instance the parallax will in many cases constrain the luminosity classification, which in turn might influence the optimisation of the MBP system. The photometric analysis is sensitive to the effects of unresolved binaries, and the possibility to detect such systems astrometrically is therefore also of great interest.

The GAIA study report provides formulae to compute the expected precision of parallaxes and proper motions as function of magnitude and ecliptic latitude. This was thoroughly discussed

on the first day. Although more detailed accuracy predictions are possible from simulations at the level of individual transits, it was concluded that this was not needed at the present stage of the analysis.

Another topic discussed was the astrometric ability to detect binaries. Reference was made to the Hipparcos paper by Soderhjelm (Ap&SS 110, 77, 1985) and more recent GAIA simulations by Quist (preprint 2001). [Comment added by Lindegren: For general modelling it would be convenient to have a simple means to estimate whether a given system can be detected or not, without having to simulate the detailed scanning etc. We are working on such a criterion.]

2. Requirements on BBP for chromaticity correction

In the evaluation of the MBP systems the use of BBP data was also considered. With the present baseline BBP filter choice (essentially five wide, adjacent rectangular bands covering the entire CCD wavelength region) it was found that the BBP contributes almost nothing to the photometric classification, not even at the faintest magnitudes. [However, it should also be remembered that the BBP has 10 times higher spatial resolution than the MBP.] Thus, ideas have emerged how the BBP filters could perhaps be modified to serve the photometry better. Unfortunately, this would typically lead to gaps between the passbands, which according to Lindegren is unacceptable in view of the chromaticity correction (quasar emission lines could fall in these gaps).

A draft action from the Copenhagen Workshop (21–2 March 2001) suggested that an attempt should be made to first optimise the BBP from the photometric viewpoint, and then see if the resulting system was acceptable for chromaticity. It was later agreed to reverse this, viz. to try to specify the astrometric requirements first, and then see what could be made with the photometry.

The astrometric requirements on the BBP was discussed at length in Lund. During the discussions it became clear that this requirement can be formulated quite simply: the BBP must provide an adequate sampling of the spectrum, no matter how complicated the spectrum is. What "adequate" means, i.e. the required spectral resolution, remains to be determined by separate analysis, but once this has been done, the sampling theorem tells how the filter must be chosen in order to preserve the information at the selected resolution. In this context the papers on photometric transformation theory by A.T. Young (A&A 257, 366, 1992; A&A 288, 683, 1994) are very instructive. After further discussion, it was agreed that a set of overlapping cosine-bell-shaped filter bands might be a good choice. This system will be evaluated by Lindegren from the chromaticity viewpoint (Action 3) and by Vansevicius from the photometric viewpoint (Action 4).

Another point which was briefly discussed is that it may be necessary to restrict (or rather, more sharply define) the wide G band (used for astrometry) by means of cut-off wavelengths, at least on the red side. The reason is that the QE curve falls off too slowly

to form a well-defined photometric band (in Young's terminology, it violates the "logconcavity" condition for well-defined spectral moments). Also, the red tail may be strongly variable between chips and as function of other parameters. The passband cut-off probably must be implemented by a thin coating directly on the CCD, not as a separate filter, lest the astrometry could be affected.

3. Improvements to the classification algorithm

The current classification method is quite straightforward: it compares the observed colour indices with synthetic indices for a very large number of model spectra and looks for the best match based on a weighted least-squares criterion. This is an accurate and robust method, but computationally very inefficient as a very large number of comparisons must be made for each observed set of colour indices. Possible improvements were discussed.

Some time ago, Lindegren suggested that the comparison should be made directly on the magnitudes of the different filter bands, rather than the colour indices. The motivation was (1) that it is not obvious which indices are best to use (at the moment only the indices from adjacent bands are used), and (2) that the photon noise errors are uncorrelated for the magnitudes, but not for the indices, which in principle makes any least-squares criterion based on colour matching dubious and probably sub-optimal. This variant of the spectral matching technique will be tested by the Vilnius group (although no action was formulated). This might improve the accuracy of the classification, but not the efficiency.

An obvious way to improve computational efficiency would be to do the classification by means of a neural network. At best it could be as accurate as the spectral matching, but providing the answer by a direct (and very fast) calculation - once the training (weight optimisation) has been done. Lindegren suggested that Bayesian training methods should be considered.

Actions:

1. Lindegren to draft a report of the Lund meeting (herewith completed)
2. Vasevicius to report to Perryman about planned participation of the Vilnius group in GAIA
3. Lindegren to reconsider the chromaticity problem in light of proposed BBP system (cosine filters)

4. Vasevicius to evaluate photometric performance of cosine filter system
5. Kucinskas to consider how other (astrometric) data can help classification